

Sustainable Development and its Goals in India

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Abstract

Sustainable development has become an integrating concept encompassing three issues as economic development, environmental sustainability and social inclusion. These issues are interdependent and without these issues sustainable development can't be attained. Sustainable development is necessary for the wellbeing of individuals and society. With the introduction of sustainable development, new challenges have emerged as environmental degradation, unemployment, investment, regional disparities, gender inequality, poverty, provision of safe and clean water, health facilities and basic infrastructure etc. To meet the challenging situation of widening economy and social disparities, inclusive growth is the best tool but it is a dream without agricultural development, employment generation, poverty reduction and improvement in social participation. With the help of strong national ownership, well managed policies, provision of more resources for essential services and public participation in development we can achieve sustainable development. Our paper is based on secondary data.

Keywords Sustainable development, Unsustainable development, Environment.

Introduction

Sustainable development has become an integrating concept encompassing three issues as economic development, environmental sustainability and social inclusion. These issues are interdependent and without these issues sustainable development can't be attained. Sustainable development is necessary for the wellbeing of individuals and society. The guiding principles of Sustainable development are summarized in the 5P's namely People, Planet, Peace, Prosperity and Participations. People means it is our duty to ensure that the Nation does not lag behind in the race of development in the individual and group field. Planet reflects the challenges of living within the boundaries of a planetary planet. Prosperity shows the commitment to bring modern education and technology to all parts of the world. Peace shows all countries living together under International law in the nuclear age. Partnership reflects commitment to government and society by working together cooperatively, honestly and ethically to achieve human goals. These 5P's also express the key principles of the member countries of the United Nations. With the introduction of sustainable development new challenges have emerged as economic shift to environmental degradation, unemployment, investment, regional disparities, gender inequality, poverty, provision of safe and clean water, health facilities and basic infrastructure etc. Sustainable development does not mean to stop the natural resources but it requires appropriate adjustment. "In order to achieve human development goals, "sustainable development" is an organizing principle that permits natural systems to continue providing ecosystem services and natural resources. Sustainable development aims to ensure the responsible use of natural resource, minimize environmental degradation and promote long-term ecological balance. Sustainable development, at its core, emphasizes harmony and balance for a healthy planet by acknowledging the interdependence of social, economic and environmental factors. Environmental issues, such as global warming from fossil fuels, climate change, Air pollution and deforestation and biodiversity loss directly impact the achievement of sustainable development goals.

Objective of study The main objective of this paper is to identify the goals and challenges of sustainable development.

Review of Literature For this paper, studies of various books and online literature i.e. Dr. Seilan, A. (2011). Environment and Sustainable Development: The Great Challenges of the twenty First Century, Kumar, Yogesh. (2023). Environment and Sustainable Development, The

Sustainable Development Goals Report 2024 & Klarin, T. (2018). The concept of Sustainable Development: From its Beginning to the Contemporary Issues have been reviewed.

Main Text

Sustainable Development Goals:

The Sustainable development goals are set of 17 global goals and 169 targets established by United Nations in 2015. They address various social, economic and environmental challenges with the aim of creating a more sustainable and equitable world by 2030. These goals include

- 1. Ending Poverty:** SDG1 talks about ending poverty in all its forms by 2030. Eradicating poverty completely is the biggest challenge before us. It focuses on targeting the most vulnerable people and increasing basic resources and services. The number of people living below the poverty line fell by more than half from 1990 to 2015. But the progress has been slower in region such as Southern Asia and sub Saharan Africa, where 80 percent of people live in extreme poverty.
- 2. Zero Hunger:** To achieve zero hunger requires lots of efforts to transform food system so they are sustainable, resilient and equitable. In 2023, approximately 730 million people faced hunger and 2.33 billion people experienced severe to moderate food insecurity. In 2022, near about 148 million children under the age of 5 were stunted. If this trend continue, one of five children under the age of 5 will be affected by stunting by 2030. Improving diet, nutrition, sanitation and health is an important way to halve the number of children suffering from malnutrition.
- 3. Good Health:** Most health related indicators are moving in right direction globally, but current trend are in sufficient to meet targets set for 2030. More than half of the world's population needs health services. Ensuring universal health without any financial hardship is important for a healthy life. Improving health, diet, nutrition and hygiene is a key way to halve the number of children suffering from malnutrition.
- 4. Quality Education:** Progress in SDG 4 has been slow since 2015, with only 58 percent of students worldwide achieving a minimum proficiency in reading by 2019. To achieve the National Education target by 2030, the countries needs to enroll 1.4 million children in early childhood education each year, enroll a new child in school every 2 seconds by 2030 and triple the annual progress to achieve the targeted primary education targets.
- 5. Promoting Gender Equality:** To achieve SDG'S goals by 2030 the world countries are lagging in its pursuit of gender equality. One of five girls still marry before age 18. Too many women still cannot realize the right to decide on their sexual and reproductive health. Strong commitments to change biased social norms, eliminating harmful practice and abolishing discriminatory laws are urgently needed.
- 6. Ensuring Clean Water:** In 2022 near about half of the world's population experienced severe water scarcity. Between 2015 and 2022 the proportion of the population using safe drinking water increased from 69 to 73 percent. By 2030 two billion people will live without safe drinking water, three billion people without safely managed sanitation and 1.4 billion without basic hygiene services.
- 7. Affordable And Modern Energy:** The generation of electricity from renewable energy has begun expanding at a very fast rate. The number of people lacking access to electricity dropped from 958 million in 2015 to 685 million in 2022. To achieve access to clean energy for all by 2030, important polices are needed to accelerate electrification, increase investment in renewable energy and increase energy efficiency. If policies are not changed, an estimated 660 million people will not have access to electricity by 2030.
- 8. Economic Growth:** Gross domestic products rebounded in 2021, it slowed in 2021 and is projected to stabilize through 2025. Global unemployment shows a historic low of 5 percent in 2023.
- 9. Industry Innovation:** The growth rate of the manufacturing sector has stagnated at around 2.7 percent. In this situation, small industries are facing problems in access to loan. To make progress on SDG's there is a need to promote inclusive sustainable industrialization and boost investment in research.
- 10. Reduced Inequality Among Country:** The economies of the weaker countries are growing at a slower pace than richer countries. Strengthening the participation of developing countries is vital to ensure a more inclusive and equitable economic system. To reduce inequality within countries and among countries, it is necessary to equitable resource distribution, investment in education and skill, efforts to stop discrimination, support for marginalized groups and international cooperation for fair trade and financial systems.
- 11. Sustainable Cities:** Currently more than half of the world's population lives in cities. Between 2000 and 2020, cities have expanded 3.7 times faster than their usual size. By 2050, about 70 percent of the world's population will reside in cities.

- This requires the development of affordable housing, efficient transport systems and essential social services.
12. **Responsible Consumption:** To achieve sustainable development goal 12 it is necessary to fostering circular economy models, sustainable production, practices and responsible consumption. This progress depends on robust regulatory frameworks, financial incentives and public awareness campaigns.
 13. **Climate Action:** Global warming has not slowed down. Global greenhouse gas emissions are still rising. Countries around the world are suffering from an ever-increasing number of disasters. The road map is ready to limit this relentless temperature rise to 1.5 degree Celsius and avoid the full effects of global warming, but the impact of delay will be devastating.
 14. **Life Below Water:** Efforts to address challenges from eutrophication, declining fish stocks, rising temperature and widespread pollution remain uneven. All these factors destroy habitats, diminish biodiversity and threaten coastal communication and health of marine ecosystems. Comprehensive global action is under way, yet it must accelerate.
 15. **Life On Land:** Despite improvement in sustainable forest management, global forest area is continuously decreasing. The main reason for this is the expansion of agriculture area. Along with this, illegal wildlife smuggling is continuously increasing. To deal with these challenges, immediate action is very necessary for wildlife diversity conservation. Measure should be taken to tackle challenges like climate change, loss of biodiversity, desertification and deforestation etc.
 16. **Peace, Justice And Strong Institutions:** The number of people forcibly resettled in May 2024 rises to an unprecedented 120 million. Conflicts and violent organized crime continue to rise around the world. New international claims affecting the economy have led to a greater savings deficit than initially approved.
 17. **Partnerships For The Goals:** Foreign direct investment flows to developing countries have declined. Nearly 60 percent of low income countries are facing a high risk of a recession.

Sustainable development goals provide a framework for international corporation and encourage governments, businesses and individuals to work together to create positive, lasting change. Near about 600 million people still suffering from hunger. The prevalence of malnutrition increased to 10 percent of the global population in 2021. Many countries are facing the dual challenges of overweight and malnutrition, and the global prevalence of obesity increased from 9 percent in 2005 to 16 percent in 2022, showing an alarming upward trend. None of the 193 United Nations member countries have achieved sustainable development goal two. Globally, only 16 percent of targets are expected to be achieved by 2030, while 84 percent are showing slow and limited progress. SDG 2 (Zero hunger), SDG 11 (Sustainable cities), SDG 14 (Life below water), SDG 15 (Life on land), SDG 16 (Strong institutions in peace, justice) have been derailed.

The decade of the 2020 marks the beginning of a new multipolar era in which countries around the world are achieving enormous successes in education, science and technology. But there are still huge differences in material conditions around the world. Year 2024 appears to be a crossroads of sorts. One way is the wrong path, towards deepening crisis, increasing natural disaster, widening inequalities, spreading conflicts and wars and artificial intelligence technology. While the other path is leading towards the use of digital technology to end poverty, global peace and human progress for all. If we want to move towards sustainable development, then Nations must work together. No Nation can solve the climate crisis alone, nor can it ensure peace and security alone. The 193 UN members' states have achieved a major milestone by agreeing on 17 broad goals with 169 specific targets by 2030. Financial structural deficiencies and geopolitical tensions have weakened the economy. The United Nations must be strengthened to underpin the new multipolar world. New problems for the United Nations should be addressed, such as UN parliament, new forms of global financing and new strategies for ensuring balance of law and power among the major power. For Environment sustainability, social justice and advancement in prosperity, ambitions must remain high. Second United Nations should promote the implementation of Sustainable Development goals through stronger global agreements. Third the United Nations should have capacity to finance the SDG's through new global taxes. Fourth the United Nations should represents the peoples by adding new forums of representations. Fifth the United Nations and its members should be in advance in science and technology for the human goods.

Recommendations of the Un Sustainable Development Solutions

1. Sustainable development and financing for development
 - a) The SDG Agenda should remain the core of global cooperation to 2050
 - b) The Sustainable Development Agenda should be properly financed
 - c) Countries and regions should produce medium-term sustainable development strategies
2. International peace and security

- a) The core principles of non-intervention should be reinforced and extended
- b) The UN Security Council and other UN agencies should be strengthened to keep the peace and sustain the security of member states
- c) The nuclear powers should return to the process of nuclear disarmament
- d) Systematic monitoring of UN-based multilateralism
3. Science, technology and innovation and digital cooperation
 - a) Enhancing the multilateral governance of technological risks
 - b) Universal access to vital technologies
 - c) Universal access to R&D capacities and platforms
4. Youth and future generations
 - a) Universal education for sustainable development and global citizenship (paideia)
 - b) Council of youth and future generations
5. Transforming global governance
 - a) There should be the establishment of a UN Parliamentary Assembly
 - b) Other UN subsidiary bodies should be established
 - c) The UN Security Council should be reformed in membership and powers.

Conclusion The world is currently experiencing a rise in demand for environmental resources, but the availability of these resources is being threatened by abuse and overuse. The objective of sustainable development is to encourage the type of development that minimizes adverse effects on the environment. Today, Sustainable development is an integral part of international policy, influencing businesses, governments and communities. Initiatives to raise awareness, manage resources sustainably and preserve habitat are common components of conservation efforts. How, in order to survive, humanity must forge a new bond with nature and we have to save our environment. There is a need for world wise cooperation in sustainable development. To meet the challenging situation of widening economic and social disparities, inclusive growth is the best tool but it is a dream without agricultural development, employment generation, poverty reduction and improvement in social participation. With the help of strong national ownership, well managed policies, provision of more resources for essential services and public participation in development can be good strategies in achieving sustainable development. Climate change, pollution, habitat destruction, overexploitation of natural resources and other factors are often to blame for this alarming environmental problem. Sustainable solutions require the resolution of problems with resource consumption, family planning accessibility and education; or to help promote a more responsible and sustainable approach to resource utilization, think about recycling, reducing water use and endorsing eco friendly products. It is intended strike a healthy balance among the social, economic and environmental aspects.

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